

A Room-temperature Hydrogen Gas Sensor Using Palladium-decorated Single-Walled Carbon Nanotube/Si Heterojunction

Yong Gang DU*, Hai Xia ZHENG, Hao NI

College of Science, China University of Petroleum, Qingdao, Shandong 266580, People's Republic of China

crossref <http://dx.doi.org/10.5755/j01.ms.22.2.12925>

Received 20 August 2015; accepted 28 February 2016

We report a room-temperature (RT) hydrogen gas (H_2) sensor based on palladium-decorated single-walled carbon nanotube/Si (Pd-SWNTs/Si) heterojunction. The current-voltage (I-V) curves of the Pd-SWNTs/Si heterojunction in different concentrations of H_2 were measured. The experimental results reveal that the Pd-SWNTs/Si heterojunction exhibits high H_2 response. After exposure to 0.02 %, 0.05 %, and 0.1 % H_2 for 10 min, the resistance of the heterojunction increases dramatically. The response is 122 %, 269 % and 457 %, respectively. A simple interfacial theory is used to understand the gas sensitivity results. This approach is a step toward future CNTs-based gas sensors for practical application.

Keywords: gas sensor, carbon nanotube, heterojunction.

1. INTRODUCTION

Due to its high efficiency, renewable properties, and for being environmentally friendly, hydrogen gas (H_2) provides an enormous potential solution to the current and future energy supply and environmental challenge [1]. However, H_2 is a colorless and odorless gas, with a wide explosive concentration range (4–75 %) at standard atmospheric pressure. Therefore, to ensure the safety of its generation, transport and storage, an H_2 sensor that can detect and monitor H_2 leakage is required [2]. Various metal-oxide semiconductors, such as SnO_2 [3], have been selected to fabricate H_2 sensors, which require better performance at high temperatures, resulting in high power consumption and difficulty in integration. So, it is essential to select suitable materials for fabricating H_2 sensors for detecting the content of hydrogen at room temperature (RT) in the development of a hydrogen energy industry [4].

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have attracted significant interests as a promising chemical sensing material because of their inherent properties such as its extremely small size, high strength, high electrical and thermal conductivity, and high specific surface area [5]. Recent studies show that CNTs-based gas sensor can effectively detect polar molecules at RT, such as ammonia gas (NH_3) and nitrogen dioxide (NO_2) because the electrical conductivity of CNTs changes drastically upon exposure to these gases [6, 7]. However, CNTs are insensitive to most nonpolar molecules including H_2 . Pd is considered to be an attractive H_2 sensing material because of its superior H_2 solubility at RT. In recent years, Pd as catalyst decorated on CNTs (Pd-CNTs) for H_2 sensor have been reported, and most of them are Pd-CNTs resistance-type [8]. A typical Pd-CNTs resistance-type consists of one or several pairs of electrodes that make electrical contact with the Pd-CNTs film. A change in the electrical resistance of the Pd-CNTs film upon exposure to H_2 is measured as the output signal [9]. The advantages of

resistance-type H_2 sensor include low power consumption and simple operation. However, the gas response of Pd-CNTs resistance-type H_2 sensors is not high enough for excellent gas sensors.

In this paper, we fabricated Pd nanoparticles decorated single-walled carbon nanotube/Si (Pd-SWNTs/Si) heterojunction H_2 sensor. It is found that H_2 molecules have a dramatic effect on the current-voltage (I-V) characteristics of the Pd-SWNTs/Si heterojunction at RT. Upon exposure to 0.02 %, 0.05 % and 0.1 % H_2 at RT, the interface resistance of the heterojunction is found to dramatically increase to about 122 %, 269 % and 457 %. The results show that the heterojunction has very high H_2 gas response than that of CNT-based resistance-type H_2 sensors reported previously.

2. MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTS

Carboxylic acid functionalized SWNTs (Length: 30 μm , -COOH content: 2.73 wt., purity: > 90 %) were purchased from the Xian Feng Nano Company and used without further purification. Palladium chloride ($PdCl_2$, purity: > 99.9 %) was purchased from Aladdin Inc. The mixed cellulose esters (MCE) filter membranes were purchased from Whatman Inc.

Pd-SWNTs was prepared according to a method reported previously [10, 11]. Typically, 6 mg of carboxylic acid functionalized SWNTs and 20 mg $PdCl_2$ were added to 20 ml of deionized water and sonicated for 60 min. Subsequently, 5 ml of aqueous solution of sodium borohydride ($NaBH_4$) (0.01 M) was added dropwise to the mixture as a reductant for $PdCl_2$ for 20 min to obtain Pd-SWNTs. Then, the aqueous suspension of the as-prepared Pd-SWNTs solution was magnetically stirred for two hours after adding 475 ml deionized water. Lastly, a few drops of Triton X-100 surfactant were added to disperse further Pd-SWNTs into deionized water.

* Corresponding author. Tel.: +86-532-86981169; fax: +386-532-86981169. E-mail address: duyg@upc.edu.cn (Y.G. Du)

The Pd-SWNTs/Si heterojunctions were obtained by a filtration and transfer printing method [12]. Typically, 10 ml of the as-prepared Pd-SWNTs solution was vacuum filtered through a mixed cellulose ester membrane and then a thin Pd-SWNTs film was attached on it. Both p-type and n-type Si wafers were used as substrates for transfer printing of the Pd-SWNTs films. The mixed cellulose ester membranes with Pd-SWNTs films on them were placed on the Si substrates. Then, a compressive force was applied on the mixed cellulose ester membranes during baking in an oven at 80 °C for two hours to stabilize the adhesion of the Pd-SWNTs film to the substrates. Finally, the mixed cellulose ester membranes were dissolved by acetone, thus the Pd-SWNTs/Si heterojunction were fabricated.

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Fig. 1 shows the typical scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image of the as-prepared Pd-SWNTs film on Si substrate. As seen, the film is networks constituted by randomly oriented Pd-SWNTs bundles.

Fig. 1. SEM image of Pd decorated SWNTs film on Si substrate

The I-V curves of the Pd-SWNTs/p-Si and Pd-SWNTs/n-Si heterojunctions in the air are shown in Fig. 2. All H₂ sensing experiments were investigated by exposing the heterojunctions to various concentrations H₂. The gas concentration was obtained by injecting a required quantity of H₂ gas into a homemade test chamber with the air. The I-V characteristics of the Pd-SWNTs/Si heterojunctions were measured by using the two-probe method with a Keithley 2400 sourcemeter.

Fig. 2. The I-V curves of the Pd-SWNTs/n-Si and Pd-SWNTs/p-Si heterojunction in the air

As can be seen, the I-V curve of the Pd-SWNTs/n-Si heterojunction in the air shows a good rectifying behavior [13]. As can be seen, by contrast, the I-V curve of the Pd-SWNTs/p-Si heterojunction in the air shows a poor rectifying behavior with a big leakage current under reverse bias voltage [14]. The current rectification ratio at a bias voltage of ± 1 V of the Pd-SWCNT/n-Si heterojunction

in the air is about 220 while the current rectification ratio of the Pd-SWCNT/n-Si heterojunction is only 6.

The semi-logarithm plots for the I-V curves of the Pd-SWNTs/p-Si and Pd-SWNTs/n-Si heterojunctions in the air, 0.02 %, 0.05 %, and 0.1 % H₂ are shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Semi-logarithm plots of measured I-V curves of: a—the Pd-SWNTs/p-Si; b—Pd-SWNTs/n-Si heterojunctions in the air, 0.02 %, 0.05 % and 0.1 % H₂. The insets show the I-V curves of the corresponding heterojunction

The insets show the I-V curves of the corresponding heterojunctions. As can be seen in Fig. 3 a, it is found that H₂ has an obvious effect on the I-V curves of the Pd-SWNTs/p-Si heterojunction. When the Pd-SWNTs/p-Si heterojunction is exposed to H₂, the currents decrease with increasing H₂ concentration. Relatively, the change of the reverse current is higher than that of the forward current, leading a better rectifying behavior. The current rectification ratio at ± 1 V is 13, 21 and 33 when the Pd-SWNTs/p-Si heterojunction is exposed to 0.02 %, 0.05 %, and 0.1 % H₂, respectively, at RT. Differently from the case of the Pd-SWNTs/p-Si heterojunction, as can be seen in Fig. 3 b, the reverse current decreases when the Pd-SWNTs/n-Si heterojunction is exposed to H₂ while the forward current does not always increase or decrease with increasing H₂ concentration. These phenomena could be understood by the interfacial effects between Pd-SWNT film and Si substrate. When the Pd-SWNTs/Si heterojunction are exposed to H₂, Pd nanoparticle absorbs H₂ molecules, which will lower the work function of Pd nanoparticle, leading to the enhanced Fermi level of Pd-SWNTs film. For the Pd-SWNTs/n-Si (p-Si) heterojunction, the energy difference between Fermi levels of the n-Si (p-Si) and the Pd-SWNTs will decrease (increase). Thus, the potential barrier height between the Pd-

SWNTs film and the n-Si (p-Si) substrate will decrease (increase) [13, 14]. According to the reference [15], this leads to the increase (decrease) of the currents. At the same time, the electrons from Pd nanoparticles trap and neutralize the hole-carriers in SWNTs, which increases the resistance of Pd-SWNTs film and the series resistance of the Pd-SWNTs/p-Si heterojunction [16]. That is, when the Pd-SWNTs/p-Si heterojunction is exposed to H₂, the change of barrier height leads to a decrease in the current, and so does the change of series resistance, which is always synergistic in the case of Pd-SWNTs/p-Si heterojunction. However, it is always adverse in the case of the Pd-SWNTs/n-Si heterojunction. When the Pd-SWNTs/n-Si heterojunction is exposed to H₂, the change of barrier height leads to an increase in the current, but the change of series resistance leads to a decrease in the current [16]. The current of the Pd-SWNTs₂/n-Si heterojunction will increase if the effect of barrier height is dominant. Meanwhile, the current will decrease if the effect of series resistance is dominant, as shown in Fig. 3 b.

Compared to the Pd-SWNTs/p-Si heterojunction, the currents of the Pd-SWNTs/n-Si heterojunction show smaller changes, indicating the former have a higher H₂ response. So we selected the Pd-SWNTs/p-Si heterojunction to examine further the dynamic sensing performance. The dynamic responses of the Pd-SWNTs/p-Si heterojunction at a reverse bias voltage of -1 V is shown in Fig. 4. The response is defined as:

$$\Delta R/R_{air} = (R_{H_2} - R_{air})/R_{air}, \quad (1)$$

where R_{air} and R_{H_2} are the resistances of the sensor before and after exposure to H₂, respectively. As can be seen in Fig. 4, after exposure to 0.02 %, 0.05 %, and 0.1 % H₂ for 10 min, the resistance of the heterojunction increases dramatically. The response is 122 %, 269 % and 457 %, respectively. The Pd-SWNTs/p-Si heterojunction shows very high H₂ response, which is superior to those of CNT-based resistance-type H₂ sensors reported previously. For example, Aguilar et al. got a response of 40 % to 3.3 % H₂ with Pd-SWNTs at RT and Gong et al. got a response of 115 % to 0.15 % H₂ with SWNTs/SnO₂ nano composites at 200 °C [17, 18].

Fig. 4. Dynamic responses to 0.02 %, 0.05 % and 0.1 % H₂ of the Pd-SWNTs/p-Si heterojunction at a reverse bias voltage of -1 V at room temperature

4. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, we have developed high response room temperature H₂ gas sensors based on the Pd-SWNTs/Si heterojunction. The response is 122 %, 269 % and 457 % after exposure to 0.02 %, 0.05 %, and 0.1 % H₂ for 10 min, respectively. This will facilitate the development of a new type of sensing platform.

Acknowledgement

The authors gratefully acknowledge financial support by the Fundamental Research Funds for the Central Universities (15CX02073A), the Natural Science Foundation of Shandong Province (ZR2015AQ012).

REFERENCES

1. **Rumiche, F., Wang, H.H., Indacochea, J.E.** Development of a Fast-Response/High-Sensitivity Double Wall Carbon Nanotube Nanostructured Hydrogen Sensor *Sensors and Actuators B: Chemical* 163 2012: pp. 97–106. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.snb.2012.01.015>
2. **Song, H.D., Cho, S.H., Jeon, I., Kee, C.D.** A Sensing Medium Exchangeable Hydrogen Sensor Using Lamb Waves *Sensors and Actuators B: Chemical* 162 (1) 2012: pp. 348–352. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.snb.2011.12.095>
3. **Wang, B., Zhu, L.F., Yang, Y.H., Xu, N.S., Yang, G.W.** Fabrication of a SnO₂ Nanowire Gas Sensor and Sensor Performance for Hydrogen *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C* 112 (17) 2008: pp. 6643–6647.
4. **Lin, T.C., Huang, B.R.** Palladium Nanoparticles Modified Carbon Nanotube/Nickel Composite Rods (Pd/CNT/Ni) for Hydrogen Sensing *Sensors and Actuators B: Chemical* 162 (1) 2012: pp. 108–113.
5. **Fam, D.W.H., Palaniappan, A., Tok, A.I.Y., Liedberg, B., Moochhala, S.M.** A Review on Technological Aspects Influencing Commercialization of Carbon Nanotube Sensors *Sensors and Actuators B: Chemical* 157 (1) 2011: pp. 1–7.
6. **Peng, N., Zhang, Q., Chow, C.L., Tan, O.K., Marzari, N.** Sensing Mechanisms for Carbon Nanotube Based NH₃ Gas Detection *Nano letters* 9 (4) 2009: pp. 1626–1630. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1021/nl803930w>
7. **Li, J., Lu, Y., Ye, Q., Cinke, M., Han, J., Meyyappan, M.** Carbon Nanotube Sensors for Gas and Organic Vapor Detection *Nano Letters* 3 (7) 2003: pp. 929–933.
8. **Mubeen, S., Zhang, T., Yoo, B., Deshusses, M.A., Myung, N.V.** Palladium Nanoparticles Decorated Single-Walled Carbon Nanotube Hydrogen Sensor *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C* 111 (17) 2007: pp. 6321–6327. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1021/jp067716m>
9. **Lee, J.H., Kang, W.S., Najeeb, C.K., Choi, B.S., Choi, S.W., Lee, H.J., Lee, S.S., Kim, J.H.** A Hydrogen Gas Sensor Using Single-Walled Carbon Nanotube Langmuir-Blodgett Films Decorated with Palladium Nanoparticles *Sensors and Actuators B: Chemical* 188 (1) 2013: pp. 169–175.
10. **Zilli, D., Bonelli, P.R., Cukierman, A.L.** Room Temperature Hydrogen Gas Sensor Nanocomposite Based on Pd-Decorated Multi-Walled Carbon Nanotubes Thin Films *Sensors and Actuators B: Chemical* 157 (1) 2011: pp. 169–176. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.snb.2011.03.045>

11. **Kamalakannan, R., Kamruddin, M., Tyagi, A.K., Karthika, S.** Pd Decorated Few Walled Carbon Nanotube Networks for Room Temperature Hydrogen Sensor Applications *Nanoscience, Engineering and Technology (ICONSET) 2011 International Conference on. IEEE* 2011: pp. 559–561.
12. **Jia, Y., Li, P.X., Wei, J.Q., Cao, A.Y., Wang, K.L., Li, C.L., Zhuang, D.M., Zhu, H.W., Wu, D.H.** Carbon Nanotube Films By Filtration for Nanotube-Silicon Heterojunction Solar Cells *Materials Research Bulletin* 45 (10) 2010: pp. 1401–1405.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.materresbull.2010.06.045>
13. **Jia, Y., Li, P.X., Gui, X.C., Wei, J.Q., Wang, K.L., Zhu, H.W.** Encapsulated Carbon Nanotube-Oxide-Silicon Solar Cells with Stable 10 % Efficiency *Applied Physics Letters* 98 (13) 2011: pp. 133115–133115.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1063/1.3573829>
14. **Kawano, T., Christensen, D., Chen, S., Cho, C.Y., Lin, L.W.** Formation and Characterization of Silicon/Carbon Nanotube/Silicon Heterojunctions by Local Synthesis and Assembly *Applied Physics Letters* 89 (16) 2006: pp. 163510–163510.
15. **Behnam, A., Radhakrishna, N.A., Wu, Z.C., Ural, A.** Electronic Properties of Metal-Semiconductor and Metal-Oxide-Semiconductor Structures Composed of Carbon Nanotube Film on Silicon *Applied Physics Letters* 97 (23) 2010: pp. 233105-1–233105-3.
16. **Du, Y.G., Xue, Q.Z., Zhang, Z.Y., Xia, F.J., Liu, Z.L., Xing, W.** Enhanced Hydrogen Gas Response of Pd Nanoparticles-Decorated Single Walled Carbon Nanotube film/SiO₂/Si Heterostructure *AIP Advances* 5 (2) 2015: pp. 027136-1–027136-9.
17. **García-Aguilar, J., Miguel-García, I., Berenguer-Murcia, A., Cazorla-Amorós, D.** Single wall Carbon Nanotubes Loaded With Pd And NiPd Nanoparticles for H₂ Sensing at Room Temperature *Carbon* 66 2014: pp. 599–611.
18. **Gong, J., Sun, J., Chen, Q.** Micromachined Sol-Gel Carbon Nanotube/SnO₂ Nanocomposite Hydrogen Sensor *Sensors and Actuators B: Chemical* 130 (2) 2008: pp. 829–835.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.snb.2007.10.051>